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Establishing Trust and Reliance on AI in History and Cultural Heritage Research – A social epistemology based view of the challenges of epistemically dependable multimodal AI systems for accessing collections.

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In the last two years, *trust* and *reliance* have been under discussion in social epistemology of AI use in science. The consensus is that *trust* is widely accepted as a central component of modern collaborative science. Scientists simply cannot verify and double check everything their colleagues and research collaborators do. Usually, collaboration is based on researchers having differing skillsets. Because of this, it is not feasible to expect them to be able to double-check and understand everything others are doing in their research. However, what remains under discussion is how strongly *trust* should be understood, and what requirements we have for being epistemically dependent on opaque epistemic processes like AI systems.

Much of the discussion and examples used are related to physical sciences. However, I believe that digital history and the hopes of using AI for large scale access to visual cultural heritage materials presents a non-typical case in sciences which should be looked at more closely from the social epistemology point of view. I bring this issue up as there are a lot of hopes based on AI systems in LAM industry (Libraries, Archives and Museums) for making collections more accessible for research (see e.g. Vodopivec, 2025). Similarly, there are large research infrastructure projects like DARIAH-EU which are looking into taking on board AI systems to facilitate digital social sciences, humanities, and arts research.

I begin by discussing two different social epistemology views on trusting and relying on AI in scientific research. One by Inkeri Koskinen (2023) which builds a ‘necessary trust view’ and another by Jakob Ortman (2025) which argues that we can rely epistemically on AI for specific tasks. I contrast these to the ongoing digital history and multimodality discussions about methods and infrastructure development and then discuss couple of examples of recent digital history image research employing either multimodal AI models or more traditional computer vision algorithms to showcase how history and cultural heritage research use of AI differs from the physical sciences setting discussed by the two.

1. Trust and Reliance with AI systems

In 2023 philosopher of science Inkeri Koskinen argued that “We Have no Satisfactory Social Epistemology of AI-Based Science”. Koskinen presents what she calls the ‘*necessary trust view*’, which holds that “without relationships of trust, the kind of collective knowledge production that characterises contemporary science would not be possible” (Koskinen, 2023, 459) Koskinen draws from the philosophical discussion about the role of trust in science beginning with John Hardwig’s works in the 1980’s. The general gist is that in science, justification for knowledge claims is collectively produced. This means that no single researcher has the full justification for knowledge claims. This leaves two options for justification: either only groups of communities can have knowledge or individual research do know, but “part of the justification of their beliefs is replaced by trust in their colleagues.” (Koskinen 2023, 460) The issue is that not everything can be double-checked. Collaboration happens as scientist rely on skills of other scientists without constantly evaluating their practices, often collaboration even

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creates situations where one researcher doesn't have the expertise to evaluate the work of the collaboration partner. This kind of opaque epistemic dependence is part of doing collaborative science. (Koskinen 2023, 460 referring to; Frost-Arnold 2013; and Wagenknecht 2014) This kind of opaque epistemic dependence is also what we are witnessing in the development of computational SSH research infrastructures.

Koskinen notes that the necessary trust view that she is arguing for needs a relatively 'thick' notion of trust, which "requires a clear distinction between trust and reliance, and it takes trust to be an appropriate attitude only towards full agents." (Koskinen, 2023, 461) In this schema 'trust' and 'reliance' are differentiated through the concept of responsibility. Referring to a widely accepted view from Baier (1986) she states that "we can distinguish between trust and reliance by saying that trust can be betrayed, whereas reliance can only be disappointed." (Koskinen, 2023, 461) Historiography has been (and still is) a discipline where the responsibility of the historian is emphasized. It is the historian who finds the right sources, and it is the historian who interprets the sources. She might use some methods to analyze the historical sources, but the final interpretation is done by the historian herself. The network of trust within historiography is based on full agents that are responsible for their claims. On the side of physical sciences, the collaborative practices of knowledge production have become standard way of operating, but again through networks of trust between full agents. Koskinen argues that now scientist "have become epistemically dependent, in an opaque manner, on AI applications that are not capable of taking responsibility for their actions." (Koskinen, 2023, 462)

Now with research infrastructures the intuition is that infrastructures operate like instruments do in scientific inquiry. With instruments the consensus seems to be that it is acceptable to rely on epistemically opaque instruments as "as long as there is someone who understands how the instruments work, takes responsibility of them in an epistemically acceptable manner and can be trusted." (Koskinen, 2023, 462) Ortman defines this a bit further by adding that 'someone' does not have to be an individual, a group or a network of people can also be trusted (Ortman 2025, 6). Relying on Record and Miller (2018) Koskinen notes that "a responsible scientist will not rely on an instrument implicitly, without good reasons and without following collectively accepted procedures." (Koskinen 2023, 462) What she is after here is that while we can have epistemically justified reliance on instruments, we cannot have genuine trust. Following Goldberg (2020a; 2020b) goes on to argue that when scientists use epistemically opaque instruments "they trust the people who designed and built the instruments and for whom the instruments are not epistemically opaque." (Koskinen 2023, 462) Or simply: while we depend on instruments, we trust the people who created and maintain those instruments.

Following Paul Humphreys (2009) Koskinen makes a distinction between two forms of epistemic opaqueness of processes appears in two forms. In its ordinary form the opaqueness is accidental. The researcher simply doesn't know how the process works. This can be remedied through learning. This is the kind of epistemic opaqueness that research infrastructures can address with training and support. What training and support won't solve is the essential form of epistemic opaqueness where it is impossible for the process to become transparent to a researcher. (Koskinen 2023, 464) Both Koskinen and Ortman agree that Deep Neural Networks, which most AI systems are based on are essentially opaque processes. However, they differ on how that affects the analysis of whether AI tool can be trusted/relied on.

Koskinen holds the view that for scientist to trust an essentially opaque process there needs to be a full agent, which holds the responsibility. There is a moral element in trust which we don't require when relying on objects. Ortman on the other hand argues that scientists can rely on

essentially opaque processes like deep neural networks if certain conditions are fulfilled. The main difference is that reliance does not require a full agent and that reliance is goal based. (Ortman 2025, 4) To exemplify the goal-based reliance on instruments Ortman uses the example of using a calculator to do calculations which are beyond the usual mental arithmetic capabilities. We have other options like pen and paper to do these calculations, but we choose to depend on the calculator for the purpose of calculating. For Ortman the central piece for epistemic dependence “is whether one employs something with the expectation that it supports the epistemic task at hand” (Ortman 2025, 14). For Koskinen the epistemic dependence is based on the trust that we have of the people who have designed and made the calculator.

In essence we can accept opaque epistemic dependence of instruments either by trusting the people who made and maintain the instruments, or we can rely on the instruments if there are good reasons to think that they are sufficiently reliable for the task at hand. Koskinen argues that the necessary trust view runs into problems as the people we are supposed to trust don't have full understanding of the AI black box because of the essential opaqueness of these systems. Ortman who relies on reliance shifts to evaluating the reliability of the outputs instead of requiring understanding of how the system exactly works on a fundamental level. His argument is that when researchers are epistemically dependent on opaque processes, the type of the system's opaqueness is secondary to the reliability and accuracy of that system. He bases this on notion that if a system is unreliable, the epistemic dependence would be unjustified, and (crucially) the scientist would not use the system. (Ortman 2025, 15)

To argue for this Ortman differentiates between questions of *whether* and *why* an opaque system is reliable. AI systems are essentially opaque and thus establishing the knowledge of *why* they are reliable isn't possible in a satisfactory manner. However, Ortman argues that the knowledge *whether* the system is reliable can be found out. He notes that the questions of *whether* and *why* are not mutually exclusive when it comes to system's reliability. Having a good idea *why* something is reliable often works towards establishing whether it is reliable. The important part of Ortman's argument is that *whether* and *why* questions “carry differential epistemic import”. (Ortman 2025, 16) He argues that the *why* question is not what testing reliability is about, it is about *whether* the system is reliable. The benefit here is that “knowledge *whether* is a much weaker requirement than knowledge *why* and [...] can be achieved largely independently from knowledge *why*.” (Ortman 2025, 16)

The challenge is that the *whether* question is an empirical one, which means answering it will require extensive empirical testing, evaluation, and assessments by experts. Ortman leaves the door open to the possibility that there might be cases of justifying epistemic reliance where knowledge *why* is important. However, through his case example of AlphaFold (see Abramson et al. 2024 for details) he shows that knowledge *whether* a system is reliable can be enough to justify epistemic reliance. Even though he establishes that there are clearly cases where the epistemic dependence on AI is justifiable through establishing *whether* the AI system is reliable for specific tasks, he keeps the door open for more problematic cases where neither *why* nor *whether* questions can be adequately answered. He has three possible candidate cases for this found in sciences. One in high energy physics, second in neurosciences, and third in mathematics. However, I think there is a risk that the tasks that AI is hoped to help with in historiography and cultural heritage research might turn out to be of the kind in which justifying epistemic dependence turns out to be quite difficult.

2. AI based retrieval tasks in digital cultural heritage research

With the social epistemology toolkit, we gained from Koskinen's and Ortman's recent publications, I now look into couple of examples found in digital history and cultural heritage research and the suggestions that have been put forward to deal with the challenges of using AI in these fields. I think this is worthwhile for two reasons: 1) I believe AI based tools will change how image archives are accessed, and with that it will also change how physical object collections are used on research on a large scale in future. 2) There are barriers in getting researchers to widely adopt these tools. If social epistemology is on the right track, then the questions of how to get researchers to *trust* and *rely* on these tools will have to be addressed if they are to become useful for research and widely spread as part of digital infrastructures for digital social sciences and humanities.

In the last few years of digital humanities scholars have been discussing the possibilities of multimodal AI models for digital humanities. (Bateman (2017); Hiippala and Bateman (2021); Hiippala, 2021; Smits and Wevers 2023). These multimodal AI systems in digital history and cultural heritage research so far have been focused on retrieval and classification tasks. The hope is that multimodal AI models will cause a multimodal turn in digital humanities on a methodological level. For example, Thomas Smits and Melvin Wevers draw a parallel on how optical character recognition (OCR) changed the access to textual archives. They argue that in the same way multimodal models will "provide a radically new kind of bottom-up access to visual collections." (Smits and Wevers 2023, 1278) What Smits and Wevers see multimodal models being useful for are "wide range of text-to-image, image-to-text, and image-to-image retrieval and classification tasks." (Smits and Wevers 2023, 1278) This sounds reasonable, especially for researching historical sources and cultural heritage data, where large scale studies of images have been notoriously laborious endeavors. However, text-to-image, image-to-text, and image-to-image retrieval and classification tasks are quite different from the prediction tasks that AlphaFold's prediction task that Ortman based his argument on. This also means that that if researchers are to show that multimodal AI models are reliable instruments for these tasks, then we need to have ways to evaluate either *why* or *whether* the models are reliable (this kind of research is being done constantly, but it is specific kind of research beyond the skillset of most humanities scholars). Or the other option is to find a way to establish *trust* in the people/institutions that have made the model.

2.1 Addressing biases

One of the major discussion points of AI systems in research have been the biases found in these systems and the used training data (Crawford and Paglen 2019). These have been widely discussed in different contexts. In the case of cultural heritage retrieval and classification tasks Smits and Wevers offer three ways that could be used to address the biases found in multimodal models. 1) They wish to develop better ways to evaluate the influence of these biases on research through critical analysis of the models themselves and the training data used for training them. 2) They call for scholars to reflect on the effect that (historical) biases might have on specific research questions. They note that this second way is quite "normal critical historical thinking", but it requires "a basic understanding of how multimodal machine learning works." This could be simple critical questioning of, for example, if the used visual concepts have changed over time and whether the concept that a model has adopted from the training data matches a historical one. Number 3) is a more technical one which would focus on finetuning the model and its outputs itself in different ways. (Smits and Wevers 2023, 1278)

Now, these three are all reasonable suggestions for how to proceed in addressing the problem of system biases. However, based on the discussion by Koskinen and Ortman on opaque

epistemic dependence, none of the three are without challenges. Let's look at the first suggestion of critically analyzing the models and training data. This would require both knowledge *why and whether* a model is reliable. It is based on what Ortman briefly mentioned idea that "having a robust theory of *why* a system is reliable is usually conducive towards corroborating any claims about *whether* it is reliable." (Ortman 20225, 16) As we learned from Koskinen and Ortman, establishing *why* knowledge of epistemically opaque systems in effort to justify epistemic dependence either through trust or reliance doesn't work out very well. This is probably why Smits and Wevers bring in the critical evaluation of the training data as that is not essentially opaque like the model itself. This also shifts the focus on the question of *whether* the model is reliable instead of trying to find out *why* it is reliable (although this presupposes that through evaluating the training data, we can to an extent predict the model's outputs). It also becomes an empirical question. So, to establish reliability of a model through its training data would require a) access to the training data. This is problematic in cases where large commercial models have been used, but for smaller more task specific models ensuring open access to training data should be possible. b) capability to retrain the model several times to evaluate how the training data affects the model's outputs. c) specifying the tasks for which the model is used, as reliability of an instrument can be established only in a goal specified setting. This is what has been done in limited studies of historical image collections with computational tools(see e.g. Arnold and Tilton 2023). The issue is generalizing this for research infrastructural level of operations. Especially if the aim is to have a general tool that could be applied to a lot of datasets. There would basically have to be several models available which could be run to do tasks on the datasets that the researcher is working on which would then be scored against each other. Over time, reliability of different models could be established on a more general level if, for example, it is possible to track which model's outputs researchers prefer. The incorporation of the researcher also takes on board the *trust* dimension as there is a full agent onboard to take on the responsibility. However, this does not really promote the use of the tool as the reliability evaluation is left to the researchers themselves.

The second suggestion: reflecting on the effect that (historical) biases might have on specific research questions. For Smits and Wevers this is close to historical critical thinking note that this could be for example questioning if "the visual concept that we are trying to identify exist (in the same form) in the time of our sources/when the training data for the multimodal model were collected?"(Smits and Wevers, 2023, 1278) Considering the social epistemology understanding of reliability this is a good candidate for a way to make reliability evaluations. These evaluations require knowledge *whether* the model is reliable, even though they might also give some information towards establishing knowledge *why*. As Smits and Wevers note, these evaluations do require general knowledge of how multimodal AI models operate, but crucially they do not require the kind intricate understanding that is required from the developers and maintainers of such systems. Basically, we are introducing an evaluator (a full agent) between the user and the instrument whose evaluation of *whether* the system can, for example, identify a specific visual concept who we are expected to trust. This is not enough to satisfy Koskinen's necessary trust view on the AI model, but because this is a task specific evaluation of not the model, but of the training data, we might be able to base our trust on the historian. This seems to be a way to introduce trust back into the discussion. By establishing the general functions and requirements for a multimodal AI model for specific tasks like visual concept recognition, the reliability evaluation is based on historical reality and availability of training data, not on the capabilities of the essentially opaque model itself.

Also, because these evaluations are task specific, like the Smits and Wevers's example of a visual concept's temporal existence, the reliability can be established in relation to those tasks not in relation to the whole model. This task specificity is again a challenge for research infrastructure development. Every task would need to be evaluated separately for its reliability. Over time an aggregate evaluation could possibly be given to the model, but this again would require gathering a lot of evaluations either from the use cases or in some other systematic way. Another issue is that it might be impossible to evaluate the reliability of some tasks without spending extensive amounts of time doing specifically that. The issue is, for example, a text-to-image task where a researcher wishes to find all visual instantiations of a certain concept in a large uncatalogued but digitized archival collection. The first step is questioning if that is even possible based on the model's training data. If there are problems identified straight away, then the expectation is that probably the model will not be able to identify all images. This obviously leads to lower reliability evaluation, which can be reported. A more problematic case is one where based on the initial historical reality and training data evaluation it looks plausible that the model should be capable of doing the text-to-image task and when requested returns large amounts of images which match the request. How does the researcher then know if he got *all* the relevant images? The only way to be sure would be to compare the model identified group of images to the whole image collection. This would require going through the whole collection to identify all relevant images, which would make the use of the model pointless in the first place, unless one is specifically testing the model's capabilities. This implies that aggregating user reliability evaluations would only be likely for some of the possible tasks. It is quite unlikely that an uncatalogued image collection would be made available in digital form without any accompanying metadata, but it showcases that the reliability issue of using multimodal models for retrieval and cataloguing needs to be addressed somehow.

The third way to address biases that Smits and Wevers propose would be to fine-tune multimodal models or add classifiers to embeddings that the used model produces in effort better attune the model to specific data and research questions. From the social epistemology perspective this way of enhancing reliability seems highly focused on knowledge *why*. The focus is on the intricate workings of the model and fine-tuning either the model or its outputs. For research infrastructure point of view this is the most difficult way of justifying epistemic dependence through trust or reliability. This is not to say, it cannot be done. The AlphaFold example shows that a highly fine-tuned model for specific tasks can be relied on by scientists in an epistemically justifiable way. The issue is reaching that point. AlphaFold became reliable through a long-lasting competition, where computer models competed against each other every other year (CASP). After AlphaFold won, some even argued that the protein folding has been 'solved' (Thorp, 2021). Ortman uses the fact that scientists rely on certain instruments as an indication that it is epistemically justifiable to rely on those instruments. If it wasn't justifiable, then scientists would not use those instruments (Ortman 2025, 15). There is some truth to this, but for introducing new research infrastructure and establishing the justification for epistemically relying on that infrastructure, the argument is not satisfactory. Once the infrastructure is up and running and researchers use it then the argument works, but the motivation to use the infra must then either originate from some other reason than epistemic reliability or the justification for epistemic dependence must have been established prior the infrastructure provided tools becoming relied-on research instruments. So, either the instrument is more efficient than other research methods and the cases where it is unreliable are identifiable, or it has been shown to be epistemically reliable and is used because of that. Research infrastructure obviously aims to facilitate more efficient research, but for cultural

heritage collection access the challenge is to reliably establish when the multimodal models are unreliable. A good example of a success with history related deep neural network tools is the Finnish National Archives' Multicentury HTR model¹. It is highly fine-tuned model for handwritten text recognition for specific centuries for Finnish, Swedish, and English languages using specific set of characters. It is used because its efficient, the boundaries of its (un)reliability are identified and it is relatively easy to check if it has made an error. Currently there are no established ways of measuring or evaluating how well multimodal models manage to provide, for example, access to visual collections. While finetuning multimodal models will push the research forward, it is not the most direct way to establish new research infrastructure as a reliable research instrument unless there is a way to make researchers *trust* the models in the sense that Koskinen (2023) described with the necessary trust view.

Based on the understanding we have of the social epistemology of *trust* and *reliance* on AI systems as discussed by Koskinen (2023) and Ortman (2025) it seems that establishing justification for depending on epistemically opaque systems for research can only be done for specific tasks. For historical and cultural heritage research to use such systems for open ended and exploratory retrieval tasks this would seem to require specific AI systems for specific tasks and still there would need to be relatively uncomplicated way to determine *whether* the system has performed reliably in its retrieval task.

3. Theories of meaning and AI models

There is another promising strain of employing multimodal AI models for digital humanities research which links to the above discussion of finetuning models and their outputs, which has been pushed forward by multimodality scholars. They aim to guide multimodal AI with multimodality theory, for example, in image-to-text tasks run on visual (usually photographic) materials by employing metadata schemas developed in multimodality research. This could have tremendous influence on how image-to-text tasks are handled in cultural heritage research. While there are epistemic issues, like the ones discussed above, that need to be addressed. This kind of theory driven approach might be able to help with some of the social epistemology issues we have with trusting and relying on AI systems by shifting (some of) the epistemic dependence back to researchers relying on other researchers

In 2021, following Bateman (2017) and Hiippala and Bateman (2021), Tuomo Hiippala argued that it would be beneficial to let multimodality theory guide the generation of metadata schemas for distant viewing of photographs. Drawing from Aiello (2006) he relies on the concept of *semiotic resource* by contrasting it to the concept of *code* (as developed by Barthes). In Barthes' conceptualization of *code*, photographs' meaning is fixed in the sense that it is encoded in the image and gets decoded in the viewing. Depending on how one understands 'meaning', it can be argued that this is quite often the way in which historical research understands photographs as sources. The '*semiotic resource*' in turn "postulates that formal features of photography – as exemplified by composition and framing – can receive different interpretations depending on who the producers and intended consumers are, and what is being communicated using photography." (Hiippala, 2021, 149) These kinds of questions of who has produced, and for what purpose are basic parts of source criticism practiced by historians and cultural heritage researchers when engaging with e.g. archived materials. Similarly, the

¹ <https://huggingface.co/Kansallisarkisto/multicentury-htr-model>

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communication aspect of images is also often considered, especially in cases like propaganda images, so this kind of conceptualization of images' meanings are established should appear appealing for historians. However, it needs to be highlighted that these kind historical source criticism practices are not formalizing research methodologies as such, but rather an unstructured group of questions to ask when one is trying to make sense of the sources.

Now, I argue that both the 'code' and the 'semiotic resource' understanding are present in historical photographs, and this creates a tension, which I believe is at the core of doing research using images as historical sources. If computational methods like distant viewing can address this tension, then it is much more likely that they become stable options in historians' toolkits. By 'addressing' I don't mean dispersing the tension but acknowledging it and providing ways for the researcher to work on it. As noted above, neither 'code' nor 'semiotic resource' understandings are unfamiliar to historians (or cultural heritage researchers in general). The tension stems, as it is often the case when the past is being researched, from epistemic uncertainty. When historians find images in archives or personal collections, they are usually not in their original context. Newspaper archives are an obvious exception, but there are also others. The producer of an image might be easily identifiable from the collections' descriptive metadata. i.e. whose collection it is. The intended purpose and 'consumers' of the image might also be inferable from the metadata. 'A family album' kind of hints at the purpose and the people who would view it, but it might not. Unless the historian can establish these, he is left with the 'code' of the photograph. Some things must be inferable without the descriptive contextual metadata, as images are not meaningless by themselves. From this stems the tension, and it is not an either-or situation. It is not that an image either gets decoded, or that its meaning is established through contextual information; it is both. If you know the photographer, is it enough to make reliable inferences about some of the meanings of the image, or is the spatiotemporal location where the photo was taken enough to do certain interpretations? This is the metaphorical space in which historians do their work, where they make their interpretations, and where they develop their intricate understanding of the source materials they use.

From the social epistemology perspective, this is fundamentally a *trust*-based discussion of *why* a metadata generation built on a theory-based schema done with computational distant viewing methods (see Arnold and Tilton 2023) would be reliable. Based on what Koskinen and Ortman have established on *trust* and knowledge *why* in relation to epistemic opacity of deep neural networks it is not apparent how we could justify relying on AI for this kind of metadata generation. The shift in trust that Hiippala (and Bateman) are going for is establishing the trust on multimodality based theory of meaning of images rather than on a essentially opaque deep neural network. But as was shown by Koskinen (if we adopt her take on *trust*), we need a full agent, not a theoretical scheme to assign trust to. Luckily as Ortman suggested we can expand this to groups, in this case it would be the multimodality scholars who have advanced the multimodality theory based on 'semiotic resource' like Hiippala (2021), Aiello (2006), and Kress and van Leeuwen (2006) , or we could trust Roland Barthes and his conceptualization of the photographic 'code' (Barthes, 1977). The caveat is that it would still need to be established somehow *whether* the employed deep neural network actually follows the chosen theoretical schema for image-to-text tasks run for metadata generation. This would require testing, but could be, in principle, found out empirically.

For historical research, the multimodal nature of source materials is of central importance. This holds especially with materials from the era of photography, but it is worth keeping in mind that

non-textual source materials are not limited to photographs. The challenge this presents to the schema that Hiippala(and Bateman) have been arguing for is that the number of theories for establishing meaning interpreted from visual sources is quite large, which ones are we supposed to trust? This could also be seen as an opportunity, as there are a multitude of theories developed for interpreting different historical materials from a variety of periods and sources. Theory guided AI tasks would require not just incorporation of multimodality theories for establishing metadata, but also historical experts whose research methodologies and ways interpreting historical sources would have to be codified to metadata schemas which are useful for the models, which is not unproblematic.

A case example of distant viewing that goes beyond 20th and 21st century photography can be found in Meinecke et al. (2024) Where they explore the challenges of doing distant viewing with medieval manuscripts. They note that the way in which Arnold and Tilton frame distant viewing was to create computational processes that would enable the use of large image datasets in similar manner as smaller image collections are used in research. The images in medieval manuscripts differ significantly from modern photographic images on which most neural networks are trained on. Still, they find out that for example people, animals and trees “are relatively easy to detect computationally”.(Meinecke, et al. 2024, 640) Not surprisingly what they found more challenging to identify computationally were “highly specialized objects such as crowns or swords, uncommon or complex varieties of flora or fauna, or even hybrid human-animal figures or imaginary animals”. (Meinecke, et al. 2024, 640) They also note that “extra-visual information is needed to contextualize and interpret” medieval images which often “make meaning in allegorical or a narrative way”. (Meinecke, et al. 2024, 640) In other words, they point out that the meaning of the imagery in medieval manuscripts is multimodal by nature and that establishing that meaning can be quite a complex project. Luckily, these manuscripts have the extra-visual readily at hand as the images are often surrounded by text. However, when exploring labels / annotations done by archives decades ago they found them of limited use for computational processes “such as object detection or image segmentation.” (Meinecke, et al. 2024, 650) They reasoned that this was because “[t]he original labels had been designed for search and retrieval of images for forms of close viewing, rather than distant ones.” (Meinecke, et al. 2024, 650) If this is the case with other visual materials, then this points towards a possible need to re-evaluate how useful older archival metadata labels and descriptions are for computational analysis of visual materials. To address this, they subdivided “the legacy annotations into categories of different orders of complexity” by categorizing the complex vocabulary to three categories: descriptive, decorative and interpretive in effort for them to be useful for different tasks. ((Meinecke, et al. 2024, 650)

Here we begin to how the establishing meaning of images is quickly becoming a complex interplay between adopted theory of meaning² and computationally instantiating that theory to metadata structures. ‘Descriptive’ label is for qualities “that anyone, without specialized knowledge, say a child, could learn to recognize”, ‘decorative’ “refers to a set of very detailed labels that only a manuscript specialist would be proficient in”, and ‘interpretive’ is for cases where “some extra-visual context (usually textual context) is required to be able to label the item.” (Meinecke, et al. 2024, 650) This is not exactly what Hiippala (2021) argued for in pushing the ‘semiotic resource’ based understanding of the meaning of images. Still, it is clearly a step

² Note that no exact ‘theory of meaning for images’ has been explicated in the study, but Meinecke, et al. obviously have some implicit idea of how images and meaning operate which they are trying to make work computationally.

into the direction of not just decoding image data, but acknowledging the influence that context has on them. However, Meinecke, et al. do have a hypothesis that “a combination of descriptive items found in an image can “arithmetically” add up to an interpretive judgment” (Meinecke, et al. 2024, 650). This seems to instead point towards the possibility of decoding the image’s ‘code’. Once again, we have found the metaphorical space where historians (or in this case specifically medievalists) earn their pay, but now through computational research tools rather than employing a theoretical framework. This seems to strengthen Hiippala’s 2021 argument that there is a connection between multimodality theory and digital humanities at least within historical research.

3.1 Dominance of semantic meaning

To complexify the landscape of combining theories of meaning and computational tools further Smits and Wevers (2023) acknowledge that in digital humanities the separation of text and images was not conceptually driven but based on technological development. Natural language processing can analyze text while computer vision can analyze images. This means that theories of meaning which cover, for example, images and text might not translate to computationally usable metadata schemas easily. However, Smits and Wevers seem to take a stance that for images to be understandable there needs to be ways to constitute the meaning of images in text form, at least in digital humanities. They base this on fact that computer vision “techniques are still unable to bridge the ‘semantic gap’ [...] between what computational methods can extract from visual data and what these data mean to a user. In other words, we need text if we want to understand what images mean.” (Smits and Wevers 2023, 1268) I think this intuition should be explored a bit further before it is fully adopted, especially in historical research. Multimodality scholars have taken several steps towards explicating the relations between different media and how they construe meaning together. They have identified and separated from each other the three central concepts and their contributions: medium, semiotic mode, and genre (Bateman, et al 2017; Hiippala and Tseng, 2017; Hiippala 2021). However, they seem to take for granted that meaning is semantically constructed. In studying communication this is warranted, but in studying history the semantic construction of meaning needs to be a conscious decision. There are source materials where it can be assumed that meaning is obviously semantically construed, like letters, or books, or transcripts of political speeches, but this might not hold for all source materials. The ‘semantic gap’ that computer vision hasn’t so far been able to bridge, might not happen simply because the extraction process is based on the assumption that meaning in general is semantically construed. It might be just that the meanings that users associate with image data in semantic form does not actually exist in the image data; it is just expressed by the users in semantic form. This is why multimodality theory is so important also for historiography. It gives conceptual tools to make meaning inferences from images based on contextual data, and it gives tools to make expectations that people might take as the meaning of specific images in different contexts.

It is interesting that Smits and Wevers easily acknowledge that there are concepts which “are hard to describe in purely visual terms”, (Smits and Wevers 2023, 1269) but insist that images meanings should be reducible to text (Smits and Wevers 2023, 1269-1270). They refer here to abstract concepts like love or anger. Isn’t it expected that there are visual, possibly non-conceptual, information is difficult to order semantically or even conceptualize as linguistic concepts? Maybe there is even information which just cannot be conceptualized semantically, but which humans are able to identify. Now again, I am not arguing this to discredit the efforts to bridge the semantic gap in computational image analysis. What I am trying to convey here is

that it is exceedingly difficult to move away from semantic concepts in multimodal research. This is especially the case in computational humanities as the NLP based text mining has been developed based on semantics (for good reasons).

A good example of this is the finding that “[f]or this text-to-image retrieval task, it is important to note that multimodal is particularly sensitive to text on images” (Smits and Wevers 2023, 1269-1270 referring to; Radford et al., 2021).” If there is semantically organized information (e.g. text) on images, the models pick those up. This ties the image data to the semantic concept relation network. Smits and Wevers use the example (from their data) of a photograph of a dog with the text “collie” above it, which leads “the model to connect this image more easily to the prompt ‘dog’. The same would go for the prompt ‘bakery’ and a photograph where the word ‘bakery’ is visible on the storefront.” Now this is very human in the sense that, that is how humans also navigate the world. A bakery sign in show to highlight the existence of a bakery at that location. Another case where multimodal contrastive models showcase their dependence on simplified semantics are words with multiple meanings (homonyms and polysemy words). Smits and Wevers discuss two examples: ‘crane’ and ‘boxer’. They note that the traditional computer vision models have no problems with these. Construction cranes and the birds don’t really resemble each other, neither do the dogs and the pugilists. However, the contrastive multimodal models they tested “turn the word crane into a single embedding and, as a result, will connect images of both birds and machines to it.” (Smits and Wevers 2023, 1270) Now of course the practical solution would be to make several embeddings and reduce the number based on CV analysis, but this does not address the underlying issue of which is which? We might end up in a situation where all the images of the bird are embedded with the construction version of the word crane. Now this is a naive example which would most likely be picked up quite quickly, and the model could be tuned to sort it out. However, for computational humanities and complex SSH concepts where the understanding of different nuances of concepts plays a role, it could be catastrophic for our ability to epistemically trust or rely on the system, if there is a change for the embeddings to go wrong when using multimodal models. Challenges with these cases and metonymical issues with e.g. metaphors can be worked around to an extent by adding context to prompts (Smits and Wevers 2023, 1270 referring to; Radford et al. 2021). Still, this kind of possibility of unreliability is again a problem for establishing epistemic trust and justifiability of epistemic dependence on multimodal models. As noted, this can be worked around in specific research, but if a research infrastructure provides this kind of tools there needs to a way to check *whether* the model is operating reliably or not in picking up conceptual differences.

Conclusions

In this paper I have examined multimodal AI-based retrieval and classification examples in recent digital history and cultural heritage research in the light of recent developments in social epistemology of science. Building on Koskinen’s (2023) necessary trust view and Ortman’s (2025) account of reliance, I have argued that the justification epistemic dependence on AI models for e.g. text-to-image retrieval tasks needs to be established. It is a different for researcher to depend on a deep neural network for specific task and finetune a model for than it is for that researcher to rely (or trust) a new more general AI based tool provided by a research infrastructure. In physical sciences, AI tools such as AlphaFold enter settings where there are relatively clear task definitions, mature evaluation regimes, and communities accustomed to large-scale collaboration and instrument-mediated inquiry. In contrast, historical and cultural heritage research has traditionally been organised around individual projects, slow interpretive

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work, and finely grained source criticism, with only limited experience of epistemically opaque computational infrastructures.

In this context, the distinction between trust and reliance becomes particularly consequential. Koskinen's necessary trust view stresses that scientific knowledge production depends on relations of trust between full agents who can assume epistemic and moral responsibility. For historically oriented work, this fits well with the existing disciplinary norms: historians (with the help of archivists) take responsibility for source selection, interpretation, and claims. Multimodal AI systems, by contrast, are essentially opaque deep neural networks and cannot themselves be bearers of responsibility; at best, we can try to extend the trust the communities that design, maintain, and evaluate them. However, because of the essential opaqueness of AI systems it becomes increasingly hard to justify the epistemic dependence on such tools through trust. Ortman's emphasis on reliance sidesteps the need for full understanding of how such systems work, focusing instead on *whether* their outputs are sufficiently reliable for specific goals. Yet in digital cultural heritage, we currently lack robust, field-specific procedures for determining *whether* AI systems are reliable for retrieval, distant viewing, or metadata generation tasks.

The examples discussed in digital humanities research—particularly work by Smits and Wevers on multimodal models and by multimodality scholars on metadata schemas and distant viewing—show both the promise and the difficulty of integrating these tools into historical practice. Text-to-image, image-to-text, and image-to-image retrieval can radically expand access to large, under-described visual collections, the problem is establishing reliability of such systems in large scale. Currently the social epistemology understanding is that epistemic reliance on opaque systems can be justified for specific tasks. With the complexity of the retrieval tasks, it is unclear what still counts as the same task in cultural heritage context.

If we accept Ortman's insight that justifying epistemic dependence on opaque systems can, in principle, proceed by establishing whether they are reliable for specific tasks, the challenge for cultural heritage research infrastructure is how to build, document, and sustain such reliability assessments in practice. Unlike in the prime example case of using deep neural networks in scientific research AlphaFold, there is specified problem to tackle (protein folding), neither is there in existence any research community wide system for evaluating how well an AI system cultural heritage research related tasks. In history, cultural heritage, social sciences the tasks are often open-ended, and exploratory; many relevant concepts are fuzzy, historically shifting, and contested.

This leads to the main argument. If the current social epistemology of *trust* and *reliance* offers a credible understanding of how justification of epistemic dependence on AI systems then for multimodal AI-based infrastructures to be epistemically acceptable in history and cultural heritage research, they must be governed as situated, and task-specific, rather than as general-purpose systems. However, as the amount of acceptable use cases grows maybe a more general system could be relied on epistemically. However, the challenge remains that it would need to be established when the system is reliable. In other worlds there would need to be some way for a researcher to gauge *whether* the system reliable for the specific task he is planning on using it.

One option is that a research infrastructure would in some form institutionalise *task-specific reliability evaluation* for digital humanities tools and provide an updated list of testes tools. Currently this is left for individual researchers to scour through research publications in search

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of knowledge *whether* some model is usable for the task he is planning. Over time, a landscape of models with different strengths and weaknesses would probably emerge. Another option that would likely help in establishing justified epistemic dependence is establishing agents between the user and the AI system. For retrieval tasks this would likely be the data holders. i.e. archives and museums. This option focuses on *trust*. The researcher trusts the institution. If the institution offers a tool then based on the level trust the researcher has for the institution to be able to evaluate reliability of the tool he might be willing to become epistemically dependent on them. This is not a perfect solution, but it could facilitate more widely spread use of AI systems for retrieval tasks which might in turn help developing better systems.

Fundamentally the challenge in justifying epistemic dependence of AI systems in digital history and cultural heritage research is generalization. As shown by Ortman (2025) epistemic dependence on AI systems can be justified for specific tasks by establishing *whether* the system in question is reliable for that task. This does not necessarily require understanding *why* the system is reliable. However, if one wishes to expand the justification to more general AI systems then the evaluation *whether* becomes problematic as establishing it is a task specific process. It would likely become an impossible task in practice because it would require too much time. The other option is to try to establish *why* a more general AI system is reliable, but this runs into issues because of the essentially opaque nature of AI systems. Multimodality theorists have suggested the use of theories of meaning to guide how AI should perform specific tasks but because of the nature of history and cultural heritage research these theories are not uniformly agreed upon. This might still be an interesting avenue to explore as the epistemic justification could be based on the theory not the AI system. However, this would still require somehow establishing *whether* the AI model actually operates the way the theory dictates or not. Establishing this would again likely require a lot of work.

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Bibliography

Abramson, J., Adler, J., Dunger, J., Evans, R., Green, T., Pritzel, A., Ronneberger, O., Willmore, L., Ballard, A. J., Bambrick, J., Bodenstein, S. W., Evans, D. A., Hung, C.-C., O'Neill, M., Reiman, D., Tunyasuvunakool, K., Wu, Z., Žemgulytė, A., Arvaniti, E., ... Jumper, J. M. (2024). Accurate structure prediction of biomolecular interactions with AlphaFold 3. *Nature*, 630(8016), 493–500. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-07487-w>

Aiello G (2006) “Theoretical advances in critical visual analysis: perception, ideology, mythologies, and social semiotics.” *Journal of Visual Literacy* 26(2): 89–102.

Vodopivec, I (2025) “AI4LAM Artificial Intelligence for Libraries, Archives & Museums – A Collaborative Network for Reliable and Trustworthy use of AI in Libraries, Archives, and Museum’s Historical Collections” presentation in Presentation in DARIAH Annual event 2025: The Past. See also <https://sites.google.com/view/ai4lam/home>

Arnold, T and Tilton, L (2023) *Distant Viewing: Computational Exploration of Digital Images*. Cambridge, Mass & London, England: MIT Press

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17700648

Barthes, Roland. (1977) *Image—Music—Text*. Translated by Stephen Heath. New York: Hill and Wang

Bateman JA, Wildfeuer J and Hiippala T (2017) *Multimodality: Foundations, Research and Analysis – A Problem-Oriented Introduction*. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton.

CASP <https://predictioncenter.org/>

Frost-Arnold, K. (2013) “Moral Trust and Scientific Collaboration.” *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science* 44: 301–310. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.shpsa.2013.04.002>.

Goldberg, S. 2020a. “Epistemically Engineered Environments.” *Synthese* 197 (7): 2783–2802. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11229-017-1413-0>.

Goldberg, S. 2020b. “Trust and Reliance.” In *The Routledge Handbook of Trust and Philosophy*, edited by J. Simon, 97–108. New York: Routledge

Hardwig, J. (1985) “Epistemic Dependence.” *The Journal of Philosophy* 82 (7): 335–349. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2026523>.

Hardwig, J. (1991) “The Role of Trust in Knowledge.” *The Journal of Philosophy* 88 (12): 693–708. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2027007>.

Hiippala, T (2021). “Distant viewing and multimodality theory: Prospects and challenges” *Multimodality and society* 2021, vol 1(2) 134-152. p.140

Hiippala T and Tseng C (2017) “Introduction to the special issue on media expectations and genre evolution” *Discourse, Context & Media* 20: 157–159.

Humphreys, P. W. 2009. “The Philosophical Novelty of Computer Simulation Methods.” *Synthese* 169 (3): 615–626. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11229-008-9435-2>.

Koskinen, I (2023) “We Have No Satisfactory Social Epistemology of AI Based Science” *Social Epistemology*, 38:4, 458-475, DOI: 10.1080/02691728.2023.2286253

Kress G and van Leeuwen T (2006) *Reading Images: The Grammar of Visual Design*. 2nd edn. London: Routledge.

Meinecke, C Guéville, E Wrisley, D. Jänicke, s (2024) “Is medieval distant viewing possible? : Extending and enriching annotation of legacy image collections using visual analytics” *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities* 2024, 29, 638-656. p. 650

National Archives of Finland <https://huggingface.co/Kansallisarkisto/multicentury-htr-model>

Ortmann, J (2025) “Of opaque oracles: epistemic dependence on AI in science poses no novel problems for social epistemology” *Synthese* (2025) 205:80 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11229-025-04930-x> p. 15

Radford, A Kim, J W Hallacy, C et al. (2021) “Learning transferable visual models from natural language supervision” In International Conference on Machine Learning, PMLR, virtual, pp. 8748–63.

Record, I., and B. Miller. (2018) “Taking iPhone Seriously: Epistemic Technologies and the Extended Mind.” In *Extended Epistemology*, edited by J. A. Carter, 105–126. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17700648

Smits, T and Wevers, M (2023) "A multimodal turn in Digital Humanities. Using contrastive machine learning models to explore, enrich, and analyze digital visual historical collections" *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities* 38 1267-1280.

Thorp, H H (2021) "Proteins, proteins everywhere." *Science*, 374(6574), 1415–1415.
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abn5795>

Wagenknecht, S. (2014) "Opaque and Translucent Epistemic Dependence in Collaborative Scientific Practice." *Episteme* 11 (4): 475–492. <https://doi.org/10.1017/epi.2014.25>